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Pragmatic aspect of advertisement

Muxamedova Malika Qaxramon qizi

2-year magistracy student

malikapulatova03333@gmail.com

Annotation. Pragmatic aspect of advertisement explores how advertisements are crafted to effectively communicate and influence target audiences. It examines the functional use of language, pragmatic strategies, and communicative techniques aimed at achieving specific objectives. Key aspects include the clarity, brevity, and emotional appeal of messages, as well as their cultural and contextual adaptation. The study also delves into the use of connotations, persuasive elements, and implicit meanings, highlighting how these features contribute to the overall impact and effectiveness of advertising in various contexts.

Key words: pragmatic aspect , communication strategies ,target audience , persuasion , language functionality, cultural adaptation, implicit meaning , clarity, brevity, marketing communication.

Introduction. As a philosophical and practical approach, pragmatism places more emphasis on results, consequences, and practical application than on idealistic abstractions. Pragmatism in advertising refers to creating strategies and messaging that not only grab attention but also produce quantifiable outcomes. Pragmatic advertising concentrates on accomplishing these goals in the most effective and significant manner possible, whether the purpose is to boost revenue, raise brand awareness, or foster consumer loyalty. This entails answering important questions for advertisers, such as: What action do we want the audience to take? How can we interact with them in an effective manner? Which formats and platforms will effectively communicate our message? Answering these problems and adjusting to shifting customer preferences and technical developments are at the heart of pragmatic advertising. Ambiguity might confuse customers

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and lessen the advertisement's effect. Campaigns that are successful condense difficult concepts into catchy slogans or images that appeal to the target audience. For instance, Nike's "Just Do It" slogan creates a call to action that is universally understood by condensing motivation, action, and aspiration into just three words. The needs, values, and interests of the target audience must all be reflected in advertisements. A thorough grasp of customer demographics, preferences, and pain issues is necessary for this. To make sure their ads are relatable and effective, pragmatic advertisers develop profiles of their target clients using methods like market research, polls, and data analytics.

Materials and Methods. The study of advertising language and its pragmatic aspects is very important for ensuring successful communication in the field of advertising. Pragmatics studies how language works in a social context, that is, how it affects the target audience. The pragmatic aspects of advertising focus not only on the aesthetic aspects of advertising, but also on the ways in which it communicates with the audience and achieves its goals.

M.Y.Azarova. (2019) The scientific work "Pragmatics of Advertising" examines the pragmatic analysis of advertising language and its role in establishing communication with the audience. Azarova analyzes the relevance, semantic and syntactic means of advertising language from a pragmatic perspective. The analysis focuses on how advertising texts successfully establish relationships with the target audience. In this work, the advertising language, its specific features, and contextual variations of language are analyzed.

A.A.Makarov. (2020) The book "The Pragmatics of Persuasion in Advertising" examines persuasive techniques in advertising and their pragmatic aspects. Makarov conducted a pragmatic analysis of the psychological and linguistic strategies used in advertising. Makarov analyzes the persuasive elements in advertising texts, including how to use language, how to influence the audience through visual and linguistic means.

J.R.Searle (2018) In his book "Linguistic Pragmatics of Advertising Language", he explains the linguistic foundations of the pragmatic use of language in advertising. Searle considers various forms of communicative activity in advertising texts. The accuracy, delivery, and coherence of communication play a key role in analyzing the pragmatic purposes of words and phrases in advertising language. Searle considers the connection between text and context to be of great importance in his analysis.

M.N.Sadykova (2021) conducts a pragmatic analysis of print advertisements in her study. Sadykova studies the impact of advertising language

on specific groups, including age, gender, and social status. The analysis examines linguistic connections between advertisements, as well as stylistic devices used in print advertisements and their impact on the audience.

A well-crafted CTA is essential for converting interest into action. Pragmatic advertising ensures that CTAs are visible, compelling, and aligned with the campaign's objectives. Whether it's "Buy Now," "Learn More," or "Subscribe Today," a good CTA provides clear next steps for the consumer, reducing friction in the decision-making process. Selecting the appropriate channels for advertising is essential in the fragmented media environment of today. To find out where their target audience is most likely to interact with their material, pragmatists evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of a variety of platforms, including email marketing, social media, search engines, and television. Context is important, and pragmatic advertising understands this. Campaigns are designed to fit the economic, social, and cultural context in which they are launched. For instance, in order to prevent misunderstandings, ads in one nation might need to be completely redesigned for a different cultural setting. Advertising uses language, visuals, and symbols in a very practical way. Words and images that arouse particular feelings or concepts are carefully chosen by advertisers. For example, premium businesses frequently communicate exclusivity and status through refined language and austere designs. To convince viewers, effective ads use pathos (emotional appeal), ethos (credibility), and logos (logical argumentation). These strategies are used pragmatically to align with the objectives of the campaign and the expectations of the target audience. The foundation of pragmatic advertising is an understanding of consumer psychology. Decision-making is influenced by ideas such as scarcity, social proof, and loss aversion. Pragmatic advertising has been transformed by the emergence of big data. Now that they have access to real-time data on customer behavior, advertisers may create customized ads.

Results. M.Y.Azarova. (2019) in her scientific work studies pragmatic tools for conveying clear and understandable messages in advertisements, manipulating the audience and gaining a competitive advantage. The influence of personal and cultural contexts, language flexibility and advertising strategies in attracting the target audience is discussed.

A.A.Makarov. (2020) in her scientific work deeply analyzes the psychological aspects of advertising and how language is used to persuade the

audience. As a result, clear and effective communication methods are discussed to change the audience's opinion and achieve the goal through advertising.

J.R. Searle (2018) in his scientific work on the analysis of linguistic and pragmatic aspects of advertising texts shows that for advertising to be successful, not only language is needed, but also the audience, context and successful organization of communication.

M.N.Sadykova (2021) in her scientific work shows how print advertising texts use variable stylistic and linguistic means to attract the audience. The perfect advertising language should be appropriate to the needs and cultural characteristics of the audience.

Actionable data from tools like social media insights, CRM systems, and Google Analytics aids advertisers in refining their tactics. Storytelling helps to reconcile pragmatic with creativity.

Coca-Cola's holiday advertising efforts, for example, frequently include touching stories that arouse feelings of joy and nostalgia, strengthening their emotional bonds with customers. Highly tailored and effective campaigns are made possible by emerging technologies like programmatic advertising, augmented reality, and artificial intelligence (AI). AI-powered algorithms, for instance, may forecast customer preferences and provide tailored suggestions, improving the user experience in general.

Discussion. Adapting quickly to changes in the market is another aspect of pragmatic advertising. Real-time ad placements coupled with dynamic pricing tactics enable advertisers to maintain their competitiveness while optimizing income. Sustaining creativity while guaranteeing useful results is a frequent problem in pragmatic advertising. While an overemphasis on creativity may take away from quantifiable outcomes, an overemphasis on data and metrics might hinder innovation. The application of persuasive strategies brings up moral concerns regarding consumer autonomy and manipulation. To preserve credibility and trust, savvy advertisers need to properly handle these problems. In order to avoid hurting viewers or miscommunicating their message, advertisers working in varied areas need to take cultural variations into consideration. Extensive research and localization efforts are necessary for this. Customers are growing less receptive to conventional advertising techniques as a result of the widespread use of commercials across various platforms. Sensible marketers must come up with creative strategies to grab viewers' interest without boring them. *Apple's "Shot on iPhone" Campaign: This campaign leveraged user-generated content to showcase the quality of iPhone cameras, combining authenticity with a clear,*

practical message. Old Spice's "The Man Your Man Could Smell Like": This campaign used humor and targeted both men and women, resulting in a significant sales boost and brand revitalization. Pepsi's Kendall Jenner Ad: Despite its high production value, this campaign was criticized for trivializing social justice movements, highlighting the importance of cultural sensitivity. McDonald's 2017 U.K. Ad: The use of a grieving child's loss to promote a product was deemed inappropriate, showcasing the risks of crossing ethical boundaries.

Conclusion. The pragmatic aspects of advertising lie at the intersection of several fields, including linguistics, psychology, and sociology. Pragmatic analysis of advertising language identifies effective ways to influence the audience. Research shows that if the linguistic and visual means in advertising texts are correctly selected, effective communication with the audience can be established. The main goal of advertising is to introduce a product or service to consumers and encourage them to purchase it. For this, it is very important to know and correctly apply pragmatic strategies.

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Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

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